

Temperature dependence of the mode Grüneisen parameter in the vicinity of the λ -transition point in NH_4Cl

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Abstract : This study gives our relations between the specific heat C_p and the Raman frequency shifts $(1/\nu)(\partial\nu/\partial T)_p$ for the lattice modes of ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}), when the mode Grüneisen parameter γ_p depends on the temperature near the λ -transition in NH_4Cl ($T_\lambda = 242.5\text{ K}$, $P = 0$).

From our linear relations between C_p and $(1/\nu)(\partial\nu/\partial T)_p$, we deduce the values of the slope $(dP/dT)_\lambda$ for both lattice modes in this crystal. Our $(dP/dT)_\lambda$ values remain almost the same as those which we calculate when γ_p is taken as a constant close to the λ -transition in NH_4Cl . Our calculated values for $(dP/dT)_\lambda$ are reasonable in compared to the experimental values.

Keywords : Mode Grüneisen parameter, λ -transition point, ammonium chloride.

Ammonium chloride is an interesting system to study since it exhibits the λ -phase transition at $T_\lambda \cong 241\text{ K}$ at atmospheric pressure from the disordered β -phase to the ferro-ordered δ -phase. All the NH_4^+ ions are orientated randomly between two equivalent energy states in the disordered β -phase^{1,2}, whereas they are orientated parallel to each other in the ferro-ordered δ -phase.

It has been observed experimentally³ that NH_4Cl exhibits a tricritical phase transition as the pressure increases up to $\approx 1.6\text{ kbar}$. This transition is between first order ($P = 0\text{ kbar}$) and second order ($P = 2.8\text{ kbar}$) phase transitions in this crystalline system. As the pressure increases further up to about 2.8 kbar , a second order phase transition occurs in NH_4Cl where the critical behaviour changes from a discontinuous (first order phase transition) to a continuous one.

There have been a great deal of experimental studies on the λ -phase transition in NH_4Cl ⁴⁻²², as we have reviewed some of those studies in our earlier work²³. Among those, the thermodynamic properties such as the thermal expansivity⁴⁻⁷, heat capacity⁸⁻¹¹ and the P - T phase diagrams in NH_4Cl ¹²⁻¹⁵ and X - T phase diagrams in the mixed crystals of $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}_{1-x}\text{Br}_x$ ^{10,16,17} have been studied. Raman spectra¹⁸⁻²¹, neutron scattering^{1,2} and ultrasonic²² investigations have been reported in the literature.

NH_4Cl has also been attractive since Pippard²⁴ first

applied his relations to this crystalline system in the vicinity of its λ point ($P = 0$). A number of systems exhibiting the λ -phase transition have been examined by means of the Pippard relations after Pippard applied his relations to the NH_4Cl . The Pippard relations establish the correlations between the specific heat C_p , the thermal expansivity α_p and the isothermal compressibility κ_T near the λ -phase transitions and they have been studied for the following systems : liquid helium²⁵, a re-examination of NH_4Cl ²⁶, the α - β transition in quartz²⁷, liquid sulphur²⁸, sodium nitrite²⁹, NaNO_2 ³⁰ and molecular crystalline systems³¹ of KMnF_3 , CsPbCl_3 and CsPbBr_3 .

According to the Pippard relations, the specific heat C_p varies linearly with the thermal expansivity α_p and also α_p varies with the isothermal compressibility κ_T linearly in the vicinity of the λ -transition. Thus, those thermodynamic quantities can have similar critical behaviour close to the phase transitions. In order to describe the critical behaviour of the physical quantities considered, we correlate here the specific heat C_p to the Raman frequency shifts $(1/\nu)(\partial\nu/\partial T)_p$ by means of the first Pippard relation expressed in terms of the spectroscopic parameters when the mode Grüneisen parameter depends on temperature. We have introduced and applied spectroscopically modified Pippard relations to ammonium halides³². We have also applied the Pippard relations to

NaNO₂³³⁻³⁵ and liquid sulphur³⁶. Very recently, we have reported the applications of the spectroscopic modifications of the Pippard relations for solid ammonia I³⁷, solid ammonia II³⁸ and ice I³⁹ when the mode Grüneisen parameter is constant, and also for hexagonal ice⁴⁰ when the mode Grüneisen parameter depends on temperature and pressure near the melting point.

In this study we apply the spectroscopic modification of the first Pippard relation to NH₄Cl by considering the Raman frequencies of ν₅ (144 cm⁻¹) and ν₅ (174 cm⁻¹) modes in this crystal close to the λ-transition point, when the mode Grüneisen parameter depends on temperature. We first calculate the Raman frequency shifts of those modes at various temperatures between 236 and 241 K (*P* = 0) in the ordered δ-phase, and then correlate them to the specific heat (*C_p* vs (1/ν)(∂ν/∂*T*)_{*p*}) in NH₄Cl through the first Pippard relation modified spectroscopically. The specific heat data for NH₄Cl⁴¹ are used in our relation.

Theory :

Near the λ-point for NH₄Cl, the Pippard relations²⁴ can be written as

$$C_p = T \left(\frac{dP}{dT} \right)_\lambda \nu \alpha_p + T \left(\frac{dS}{dT} \right)_\lambda \quad (1)$$

and

$$\alpha_p = \left(\frac{dP}{dT} \right)_\lambda \kappa_T + \frac{1}{V} \left(\frac{dV}{dT} \right)_\lambda \quad (2)$$

where *C_p*, α_{*p*} and κ_{*T*} represent the specific heat, thermal expansivity and isothermal compressibility, respectively. Since the specific heat *C_p* varies linearly with the thermal expansivity α_{*p*} (eq. (1)), this assumes that *C_p* has similar critical behaviour as α_{*p*} ≡ (1/*V*)(∂*V*/∂*T*)_{*p*}.

Also, α_{*p*} has similar critical behaviour as the isothermal compressibility, κ_{*T*} ≡ -(1/*V*)(∂*V*/∂*P*)_{*T*}, according to eq. (2) close to the λ-phase transition in NH₄Cl. By means of eqs. (1) and (2), the slope (d*P*/d*T*)_λ can be deduced at the λ-point for NH₄Cl.

The Pippard relations (eqs. (1) and (2)) can be modified spectroscopically by defining the isobaric mode Grüneisen parameter as

$$\gamma_p(T) = -\frac{1}{\alpha_p(T)} \frac{1}{\nu} \left(\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial T} \right)_p \quad (3)$$

where the mode Grüneisen parameter varies with the temperature close to the phase transitions. Thus, the first

Pippard relation (eq. (1)), will be written as

$$C_p = -\frac{TV}{\gamma_p(T)} \left(\frac{dP}{dT} \right)_\lambda \frac{1}{\nu} \left(\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial T} \right)_p + T \left(\frac{dS}{dT} \right)_\lambda \quad (4)$$

when we substitute γ_{*p*}(*T*) (eq. (3)) into eq. (1). According to eq. (4), the specific heat *C_p* varies linearly with the Raman frequency shifts (1/ν)(∂ν/∂*T*)_{*p*} as the mode Grüneisen parameter depends upon temperature close to λ-point in NH₄Cl. On the basis of the spectroscopically modified Pippard relation (eq. (4)), it is then assumed that the specific heat *C_p* has similar critical behaviour as the frequency shifts (1/ν)(∂ν/∂*T*)_{*p*} for NH₄Cl near the λ-point.

The temperature dependence of the mode Grüneisen parameter γ_{*p*} can be expressed as a linear relation

$$\gamma_p(T) = b_0 + b_1 T \quad (5)$$

where *b*₀ and *b*₁ are constants, according to the experimental values measured for γ_{*i*} (mode Grüneisen parameter) in the disordered β and the ordered γ phases of NH₄Cl⁴². Thus, using the temperature dependence of the mode Grüneisen parameter γ_{*p*}(*T*) (eq. (5)), the first Pippard relation (eq. (4)) can be established by calculating the frequency shifts through the relation

$$\nu_p(T) = \Delta_p + A(P) + \nu_1 \exp \left[-\gamma_p(T) \ln \frac{V_p(T)}{V_1} \right] \quad (6)$$

This volume dependence of the frequency can be obtained by integrating eq. (3) with the additional terms of Δ_{*p*} and *A*(*P*). Here Δ_{*p*} = 0 for *T* > *T*_λ and Δ_{*p*} ≠ 0 for *T* ≤ *T*_λ, as the order-disorder contribution to the frequency. The pressure-dependent term *A*(*P*) can be expressed in a quadratic form

$$A(P) = a_0 + a_1 P + a_2 P^2 \quad (7)$$

with the constants *a*₀, *a*₁ and *a*₂, as we have also introduced in our earlier study²³. In eq. (6) ν₁ and *V*₁ denote the values of the frequency and the crystal volume at room temperature (*T* = 296 K).

Results and discussion

In this study we examined the validity of the first Pippard relation modified spectroscopically (eq. (4)) as the mode Grüneisen parameter γ_{*p*} varies with the temperature. For this verification, we first calculated the Raman frequencies of ν₅ (144 cm⁻¹) and ν₅ (174 cm⁻¹) modes by means of eq. (6) using the length-change data

$L_p(T)/L_1^6$ at various temperatures between 236 K and 241 K in the ordered δ -phase at zero pressure in NH_4Cl . Since the mode Grüneisen parameter γ_p depends upon the temperature, we determined the values of the coefficients b_0 and b_1 according to eq. (5) using the experimental values of γ_p (or γ_i) which were measured at 246 K and 255 K in the disordered β -phase for both the Raman modes of ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) in NH_4Cl ⁴². Our calculated values of b_0 and b_1 together with the measured values of γ_p ⁴² for both Raman modes studied, are given in Table 1. The Raman frequencies of ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and

Table 1. Values of the coefficients b_0 and b_1 using the experimental values of γ_p ⁴² measured at two temperatures for the Raman modes indicated in NH_4Cl ($P = 0$), according to eq. (5)

Raman modes	T (K)	γ_p	b_0	b_1 (K^{-1})
ν_5 (144 cm^{-1})	246	12.8	242.4	-0.9333
	255	4.4		
ν_5 (174 cm^{-1})	246	6.9	99.831	-0.3777
	255	3.5		

ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) modes were then calculated by inserting into eq. (6), eq. (5) with the values of b_0 and b_1 (Table 1), the length-change data⁶, our values of ν_1 , Δ_p and $A(P)$ as given in Table 2 (see also in our earlier study⁴³) for both Raman modes considered at various temperatures between 236 K and 241 K ($P = 0$) in NH_4Cl . In Table 2, γ_p values for both ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) modes, are also given as constant values which were used to calculate the Raman frequencies of those phonon modes⁴³.

Once, we calculated the Raman frequencies of the ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) modes through eq. (6), we were then able to deduce the Raman frequency shifts between 236 and 241 K ($P = 0$) for both modes in NH_4Cl . We then plotted the specific heat C_p as a function of the Raman frequency shifts $\{1/\gamma_p(T)\nu\}\{(\partial\nu/\partial T)_p\}$ for the ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) modes of NH_4Cl in Figs. 1

and 2, respectively, according to eq. (4). The specific heat C_p data⁴¹ for NH_4Cl were used for the temperatures between 236 and 241 K ($P = 0$) in our plots (Figs. 1 and 2).

From our plots, we were able to obtain the values of the slope $(dP/dT)_\lambda$ at the λ -point in NH_4Cl for the ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) modes, as tabulated in

Fig. 1. Specific heat C_p as a function of the Raman frequency shifts $\{1/\gamma_p(T)\nu\}\{(\partial\nu/\partial T)_p\}$ for the Raman mode of ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) in NH_4Cl at various temperatures close to the λ -point ($T_\lambda = 242.5$, $P = 0$), according to eq. (4). The C_p data are due to Amitin *et al.*⁴¹

Table 2. Values of the frequency ν_1 at 296 K, constant mode Grüneisen parameter γ_p , the pressure-dependent term $A(P)$ and the order-disorder contribution Δ_p to the frequency for the Raman modes indicated in NH_4Cl ($P = 0$) according to eq. (6). This data is taken from our previous work²³. Our values of the slope $(dP/dT)_\lambda$ deduced from the spectroscopically modified Pippard relation (eq. (4)) when γ_p is constant^{32,45,46} and $\gamma_p(T)$ is a function of temperature for the modes studied in NH_4Cl .

Raman modes	ν_1 (cm^{-1})	γ_p	$A(P)$ (cm^{-1})	Δ_p (cm^{-1})	$\gamma_p(\text{Constant})$ ($dP/dT)_\lambda$ (bar/K)	$\gamma_p(T)$ ($dP/dT)_\lambda$ (bar/K)
ν_5 (144 cm^{-1})	140.80	2.1	-0.09	1.63	102.65	103.8
ν_1 (174 cm^{-1})	167.47	2.5	-0.141	0.75	105.5	104.2

Fig. 2. Specific heat C_p as a function of the Raman frequency shifts $\{1/\gamma_p(T)\nu\}\{(\partial\nu/\partial T)_p\}$ for the Raman mode of ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) in NH_4Cl at various temperatures close to the λ -point ($T_\lambda = 242.5$, $P = 0$), according to eq. (4). The C_p data are due to Amtin *et al.*⁴¹.

Table 2. In Table 2 we also give our calculated values of $(dP/dT)_\lambda$ when the mode Grüneisen parameter γ_p was taken as a constant for both ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) Raman modes in NH_4Cl ³². In order to deduce the $(dP/dT)_\lambda$ values from our plots (Figs. 1 and 2), we used the volume value of $V = 34.72 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$ ⁴⁴ at $T_\lambda = 242.5 \text{ K}$ ($P = 0$) in NH_4Cl .

We studied here a linear variation of the specific heat C_p with the frequency shifts $(1/\nu)(\partial\nu/\partial T)_p$ for the Raman modes of ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) close to the λ -point in NH_4Cl according to eq. (4) when the mode Grüneisen parameter γ_p depends on the temperature. This analysis was performed for the temperature range of 236 and 241 K at atmospheric pressure in the ordered δ -phase of NH_4Cl . The Raman frequency shifts of those phonon modes considered were calculated through eq. (6) where the length-change data⁶ were used with the values of the additional terms (Table 2), as stated above. Differently

from our earlier studies for NH_4Cl ^{32,45,46}, in order to calculate the Raman frequencies of the ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) modes in this crystal, we introduced in eq. (6) the temperature dependence of the mode Grüneisen parameter $\gamma_p(T)$ for each mode studied here, as we have also considered for hexagonal ice⁴⁰. This temperature dependence of the mode Grüneisen parameter was taken as a linear relation (eq. (5)) on the basis of the experimental values of γ_p ⁴², as we tabulated in Table 1. Those values of γ_p were measured at two constant temperatures of 246 and 255 K for the ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) modes at 1 bar in the disordered β -phase of NH_4Cl ⁴². Using those measured values of γ_p , we determined the coefficients b_0 and b_1 for each mode (Table 1) according to eq. (5). We then predicted the Raman frequencies $\nu_p(T)$ and also the frequency shifts $(1/\nu)(\partial\nu/\partial T)_p$ for both phonon modes through eq. (6) using those values of b_0 and b_1 for the temperatures between 236 and 241 K in the ordered δ -phase of NH_4Cl at zero pressure. We assumed here that the temperature dependence of the mode Grüneisen parameter should have the same functional form in both the disordered β and the ordered δ -phases in NH_4Cl . This assumption was in fact reasonable in the sense that γ_p values measured at the same temperatures, namely, 246 and 255 K at $P = 2 \text{ kbar}$ ⁴² for the ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) modes in the ordered δ -phase of NH_4Cl , can also be expressed as a linear relation such as eq. (5).

As shown in Figs. 1 and 2, we obtained a linear variation of the specific heat C_p with the frequency shifts $(1/\nu)(\partial\nu/\partial T)_p$ for both ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) modes, respectively, near the λ -point in NH_4Cl . This shows the validity of our spectroscopically modified Pippard relation (eq. (4)) also in the case of the mode Grüneisen parameter $\gamma_p(T)$ dependent upon the temperature for the λ -phase transition in NH_4Cl ($P = 0$).

From those linearities, we were able to deduce the values of the slope $(dP/dT)_\lambda$ at the λ -point for both modes of ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) in NH_4Cl , as tabulated in Table 2. As we see from Table 2, our present values of $(dP/dT)_\lambda$ are very close to those which we obtained in our earlier studies^{32,46} when the γ_p was taken as a constant. All our values for $(dP/dT)_\lambda$ when γ_p is constant and when γ_p is a function of temperature, which we deduced for the ν_5 (144 cm^{-1}) and ν_5 (174 cm^{-1}) modes in NH_4Cl , can be compared with the experimental values of 108.8 bar/deg due to Bridgman's measurements⁴⁷ and 116.9 bar/deg from an analysis of the experimental data for C_p against α_p ²⁶ in NH_4Cl ($P = 0$).

Conclusions :

We correlated here the specific heat C_p linearly with the Raman frequency shifts $(1/\nu)(\partial\nu/\partial T)_p$ for the two lattice modes in NH_4Cl close to its λ -point ($T_\lambda = 242.5 \text{ K}$, $P = 0$) when the mode Grüneisen parameter depends on the temperature. From our correlations, we deduced the values of the slope $(dP/dT)_\lambda$ at the λ -point for both phonon modes, which are very close to our previous results when the mode Grüneisen parameter remains constant throughout the λ -phase transition in NH_4Cl . Our values for the slope $(dP/dT)_\lambda$ in both cases (γ_p depends on temperature and it is constant), are also not far from the experimental values. This shows that the temperature dependence of the mode Grüneisen parameter does not change considerably linearity between the specific heat and the Raman frequency shifts for those lattice modes studied here close to the λ -point in NH_4Cl . On this basis, we conclude that the specific heat and the Raman frequency shifts exhibit similar critical behaviour near the λ -phase transition in NH_4Cl . This then leads us to predict the specific heat from the Raman frequency shifts in this-crystalline system for its λ -transition.

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